

Markov Random Field Linear Regression

Xintian Wu and Yonghong Yan

Oregon Graduate Institute of Science and Technology,
20000 N.W. Walker Road, P.O. Box 91000,
Portland, OR 97291-1000, USA, (xintian@cse.ogi.edu)

ABSTRACT

This paper outlines the Markov Random Field Linear Regression (MRFLR) algorithm, which combines the transformation-based adaptation and dependency-modeling technique together. The hypothesis is that the adaptation performance can be improved by explicitly modeling the correlations among acoustic parameters and applying such constraints to the transformation-matrix estimation. The correlations are modeled by Markov Random Field, and the incorporation of the correlations is under the Maximum A Posteriori framework. Experimental results show that MRFLR has significant improvement over Maximum Likelihood Linear Regression when only small amounts of adaptation data are available.

1 Introduction

Speaker adaptation technologies have been widely used in speech recognition systems that face multiple speakers. In such systems, the acoustic models are often trained to be Speaker Independent (SI). Speaker adaptation dynamically adjusts the acoustic model to more closely match the test-speaker whereby improving the recognition performance.

Maximum Likelihood Linear Regression (MLLR) [1] is by far the most widely accepted adaptation algorithm. MLLR linearly transforms (through a transformation matrix) a SI model to be test-speaker specific. The transformation matrix is estimated by maximizing the likelihood of some enrollment data. Due to the large parameter space of speech systems, quite a few amounts of enrollment data are required to robustly estimate a transformation matrix. When enrollment data are sparse, MLLR often generates poorly-structured matrices, which is a major cause of performance degradations. Therefore, it's desirable to add some constraints to the possible outputs of the MLLR estimation.

Contrast to MLLR's global changes of acoustic parameters, dependency modeling adaptation features local adjustments and smoothes of acoustic parameters according to the correlations among acoustic parameters. The correlations, estimated from the training cor-

pus, are considered as prior knowledge of acoustic models and used to constrain the adaptation. Kannan detailed some of the dependency modeling methods in his paper [2]. Although robust estimation is achieved by modeling the correlations, dependency modeling methods still require quite a few amounts of adaptation data to be effective because of the local adjustment policy.

In this paper, we present the Markov Random Field Linear Regression (MRFLR) algorithm, which is a transformation-based adaptation algorithm. The transformation matrix is estimated under the constraint of the correlations. By combining the transformation-based adaptation and dependency-modeling technique together, MRFLR achieves both fast and robust adaptation. We had presented some skeleton of the algorithm in our previous paper [3]. This paper focuses on our continuous work on this algorithm and presents more follow-up experiments.

In Section 2 and Section 3, we have a brief introduction to the MLLR and MRF adaptations. In Section 4, the algorithm of MRFLR is presented. The training and adaptation procedures are detailed in Section 5. The experimental results are shown in Section 6.

2 Maximum Likelihood Linear Regression

The idea of MLLR is to linearly transform the SI mean vectors to be test-speaker dependent. The transformation of mean vectors with a given transformation matrix W is usually:

$$\hat{u} = W\tilde{u} \quad (1)$$

where $\tilde{u}^T = [u^T \ 1]$ is the augmented mean vector.

The transformation matrix W is estimated by maximizing the *Maximum Likelihood* (ML) auxiliary function $Q(\hat{\lambda}, \lambda)$:

$$Q(\hat{\lambda}, \lambda) = \sum_m \sum_t \gamma_m(t) N(o_t; \hat{\mu}_m, \Sigma_m)$$

where $\gamma_m(t)$ is the occupation of mixture component m at time t , o_t is the speech observation at time t , and $N(\cdot)$ is the Gaussian density function.

For the diagonal variance matrix case, the close form solution for mixture Gaussian models is as follows:

$$W_i^T = [G^{(i)}]^{-1} Z_i^T \quad (2)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} Z &= \sum_m \sum_t \gamma_m(t) \Sigma_m^{-1} O_t \tilde{u}_m^T \\ g_{jl}^{(i)} &= \sum_m V_{ii}(m) D_{jl}(m) \\ V(m) &= \sum_t \gamma_m(t) \Sigma_m^{-1} \\ D(m) &= \tilde{u}_m \tilde{u}_m^T \end{aligned}$$

3 Markov Random Field

The MRF theory is a way of modeling the characteristics of random variables arranged in a two-dimensional field. In the field, a point (random variable) may show dependencies on some other points, called cliques of the point. The theory shows that the joint distribution of the field is uniquely determined by all the conditional distributions of the cliques (on their neighbors), called *local characteristics*.

Specifying the *local characteristics* is extremely difficult. This seemingly limitation of the MRF theory has been addressed by a theorem that reveals the equivalence of Markov random fields and Gibbs fields [4]. The joint distribution of a MRF Q is thus of form:

$$P(Q) = \frac{1}{Z} \exp[-\frac{\beta}{2} \sum_c V_c(Q)] \quad (3)$$

where Z is a normalizing constant and β is a scale. The summation is over all the cliques $\{c\}$; $V_c(Q)$ is called a potential function.

Shahshahani [5] suggests that the prior distribution of the acoustic model $P(\lambda)$ be modeled by a MRF. The MRF is constructed by all the mean vectors in the model. The size of the field is D by M , where D is the feature dimension and M is the number of mixture components. Each column vector is a mean vector of some mixture component. For example, the point at row p and column q refers to the p 'th dimensional value of the mean vector of mixture component q , as illustrated in Figure 1. Cliques are detected as pairs of points that show high correlations during training.

Under these conditions, the potential function $V_c(Q)$ can be defined as the least square residual:

$$V_c(Q) = \omega_c (y_c - a_c - b_c x_c)^2 \quad (4)$$

where x_c and y_c are the two points of clique c . and (a_c, b_c, ω_c) are parameters of the clique, estimated by least-square fitting of point x_c to point y_c during training. In the later referrals, we will drop the index c for notation simplicity.

Figure 1: MRF representation of allophone means

4 Markov Random Field Linear Regression

In this section, we extend the transformation estimation to be under the MAP criterion. The auxiliary function for the MAP estimation is:

$$Q(\hat{\lambda}, \lambda) = \sum_m \sum_t \gamma_m(t) N(o_t; \hat{\mu}_m, \Sigma_m) + \log P(\hat{\lambda}) \quad (5)$$

Since the partial differential of the left part of $Q(\hat{\lambda}, \lambda)$ with respect to the transformation matrix W' has been obtained in MLLR, we focus mainly on the partial differential of the prior distribution $P(\hat{\lambda})$, which is modeled by MRF (Equation 3 and Equation 4).

To successfully carry out the partial differential equation, we simplify the potential function Equation 4 by making an assumption that correlations among different feature dimensions are so small that their contributions to the potential function can be ignored. Therefore, we only need to consider correlations from the same feature dimension. The potential function can be thus re-written as:

$$V_c(Q) = \omega (\hat{u}_y - a - b \hat{u}_x)^T E^{(d)} (\hat{u}_y - a - b \hat{u}_x) \quad (6)$$

where $\hat{u}_y$ and $\hat{u}_x$ are the corresponding column vectors, and $E^{(d)}$ is a $D \times D$ delta matrix: $E_{ij}^{(d)} = \delta(i = j = d)$, with d being the row number (dimension) of point x and y in clique c .

Plug Equation 6 into Equation 3, and the partial differential can be carried out without any difficulty. The transformation matrix can be estimated by solving:

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_m \sum_t \gamma_m(t) \Sigma_m^{-1} o_t \tilde{\mu}_m^T - \beta \sum_c a \omega F^{(d)} (\tilde{\mu}_y - b \tilde{\mu}_x)^T \\ &= \sum_m \sum_t \gamma_m(t) \Sigma_m^{-1} W \tilde{\mu}_m \tilde{\mu}_m^T - \\ & \quad \beta \sum_c \omega E^{(d)} (\tilde{\mu}_y - b \tilde{\mu}_x) (\tilde{\mu}_y - b \tilde{\mu}_x)^T \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where $F^{(d)}$ is a $D \times 1$ delta vector $F_i^{(d)} = \delta(i = d)$.

Finally, we have the MRFLR estimation of the transformation matrix W' :

$$W'_i{}^T = [G'^{(i)}]^{-1} Z'_i{}^T \quad (8)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} Z' &= Z - \beta \sum_c a\omega F^{(d)}(\tilde{u}_y - b\tilde{u}_x)^T \\ g'_{jl}{}^{(i)} &= g_{jl}{}^{(i)} - \beta \sum_c V'_{ii}(c) D'_{jl}(c) \\ V'(c) &= \omega E^{(d)} \\ D'(c) &= (\tilde{u}_y - b\tilde{u}_x)(\tilde{u}_y - b\tilde{u}_x)^T \end{aligned}$$

As we can see from Equation 8, the GZ accumulators consist of a left part coming from MLLR, and a right part coming from the cliques. The left parts reflect the influence of the adaptation data while the right parts reflect the influence of the prior knowledge. When adaptation data are sparse, the right parts preserve the structural information for the matrix estimation. As more adaptation data are added, the left parts soon dominate.

5 Training and Adaptation Procedures

The training procedures are as follows:

1. A set of Speaker Dependent (SD) models are trained as samples of the MRF in the next two steps.
2. Calculate correlations between all the pairs of the field and save those cliques that show high correlations.
3. Calculate the clique parameters by the linear fitting algorithm.
4. Calculate the GZ accumulators (the right parts).

The adaptation procedures are the same as what are in MLLR except for the add-on items for the GZ accumulators.

1. Perform the EM (*Expectation Maximization*) algorithm to get the occupations for each mixture component over some adaptation data.
2. Calculate the transform matrices according to Equation 8.
3. Calculate the new mean vectors according to Equation 1.

6 Experiments

Experiments were performed on the *World Street Journal* (WSJ) 20K tasks. The acoustic front end extracted 12 mel frequency cepstral coefficients, energy, and their

first and second derivatives (total of 39 parameters) from every 10 ms frame. Cepstral mean normalization was performed on each utterance.

The standard SI284 training set was used, which contained 283 speakers, about 150 sentences for each speaker. The acoustic model was state-tied based on the decision tree algorithm and trained with the EM algorithm. The final model had 7500 states with each state 12 mixture components. This model achieved a baseline performance of *Word Error Rate* (WER) 12.6% on the ARPA Nov92 test set.

We performed MLLR adaptation for each speaker on the training set to get the 283 SD models for use in clique detection and clique parameter estimation. The clique detection phase saved 11,104,362 cliques that showed high correlations among the SD models.

To show the performance curves of MRFLR vs MLLR under different conditions, we arrange our experiments as follows:

Supervised batch adaptation mode

The supervised batch mode tests were performed on the Nov92 test set. A series of enrollment sets was generated from the Nov92 enrollment data. Figure 2 shows the performance curves of MRFLR vs MLLR. Both these two algorithms used a global transformation matrix.

Figure 2: Supervised sparse data

For the performance curve of MLLR, with adaptation data less than 6 seconds, MLLR makes a terrible estimation of the transformation matrix and the performance curve is well above the baseline due to the lack of adaptation data. In practical applications, it is desired not to turn on MLLR until the amount of adaptation data accumulates. With adaptation data from 6 to 13 seconds, MLLR begins to be effective. The adaptation performance is getting better as more adaptation data are available. With adaptation data more than 13 seconds, the performance curve becomes stable with only small glitches.

For the performance curve of MRFLR, the recognition performance is improved in all the tests (compared with the baseline), which clearly shows us the advantage of incorporating prior knowledge. From 1 second to 13 seconds, the MRFLR performance curve has a smaller slope than the MLLR curve, which indicates that MRFLR is less sensitive to the adaptation data due to the constraint of the correlations. MRFLR continuously outperforms MLLR until the amount of adaptation data reaches the 13-second point where both MRFLR and MLLR become stable. There are some *bettors and worses* during the merging period.

Unsupervised auto adaptation mode

The unsupervised auto-adaptation tests were performed on the Nov92 test set. A series of enrollment sets was generated from the same test set (using targets from a previous recognition pass). Figure 3 shows the performance curves of MRFLR and MLLR. Both methods used a global transformation matrix.

Figure 3: Unsupervised sparse data

The curves in Figure 3 are like those in Figure 2 although there are more observable glitches due to errors in the enrollment references.

For the performance curve of MLLR, with adaptation data less than 7 seconds, MLLR makes poor adaptations and the performance curve is well above the baseline. With adaptation data from 7 seconds to 12 seconds, MLLR begins to improve the recognition performance. After the 13-second point, the MLLR performance becomes stable.

Compared with the baseline, MRFLR improves the recognition performance in all the tests except the one-second test set, which again shows us the strength of utilizing knowledge constraint in speaker adaptation.

MRFLR outperforms MLLR with adaptation data less than 10 seconds. The smaller slope of the performance curve indicates that MRFLR is less sensitive to adaptation data as already observed in the supervised

experiments. MRFLR converges to the MLLR performance with more than 13 seconds adaptation data.

7 Conclusions

We extend the MLLR matrix estimation to be under the MAP criterion. The prior distribution of the acoustic model is modeled by the *Markov Random Field* theory. With a reasonable assumption, a close form solution is obtained. The resulting MRFLR adaptation has better performances with sparse adaptation data and the performances of MRFLR converge to that of MLLR with more adaptation data added. MRFLR is particularly useful in sparse adaptation data cases.

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